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COMMUNICATION ECONOMICS ORGANIZATION

24-25 December 2021 - Ukraine

3rd

PROCEEDINGS

BOOK

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Luigi Pio Leonardo Cavaliere

Dr. Ali Ahmad

Serhat Ademoğlu

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International CEO

(**C**ommunication, **E**conomics, **O**rganization)

Social Sciences Congress

PROCEEDINGS

E-BOOK

24-25 December 2021

CEOSSC 2021 - Ukraine

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Prof. Dr. Khabib Kholikovich Razzokov

Mr. Luigi Pio Leonardo Cavaliere

Serhat Ademoğlu, PhD. Candidate

Dr. Ali Ahmad

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International CEO

(Communication, Economics, Organization)

Social Sciences Congress

We are delighted to introduce Samarkand Branch of Tashkent University of Economics, International Vision University, Alfred Nobel University, International Gorazde University, Nişantaşı University, University of Prizren, Cyprus West University, Central Asian American University, Mohanlal Sukhadia University, Insec, NCM Publishing and CEO Tekmer served as the vehicle of dissemination for a showpiece of articles at the **International CEO (Communication, Economics, Organization) Social Sciences Congress (CEO SSC 2021, Ukraine)** that was held online on December 24–25, 2021. CEO Congress aims to provide a platform for discussing the issues, challenges, opportunities and findings of **Communication, Economics, Organization and Social Science** research. The organizing committee with feedback from the division chairs and the members of the **scientific committee** foresaw an opportunity and research gap in the conference theme, that pitches for pressing issues in the business world.

Presentations are in **Turkish, English & Russian**. With the participation and contributions of academics from **32 countries: Afghanistan, Argentina, Albania, Australia, Azerbaijan, Bulgaria, Indonesia, Morocco, Philippines, Georgia, India, Italy, Japan, Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus, Kyrgyzstan, Colombia, Kosovo, Macedonia, Nigeria, Uzbekistan, Pakistan, Poland, Serbia, Chile, Turkey, Romania, Srilanka, Tunisia, UK, New Zeland, Vietnam, Zambia**. It is a great privilege for us to present the proceedings of **CEO SSC 2021** to the authors and delegates of the conference.

Several manuscripts from prestigious institutions could not be accepted due to the reviewing outcomes and our capacity constraints. Participation from **114 different institutions or Universities**. The 2 days long conference gathered close to **164 national and international attendees** to enliven a constellation of contributions. 76 papers of the 112 papers approved to present at the congress are outside of Turkey. **68% of the papers presented at the congress are from outside Turkey**. 6 best paper awards were issued to distinguished papers, and a total of **112 oral presentations**.

On the day of completion of this journey, we are delighted with a **high level of satisfaction and aspiration**. It is important to offer our sincere thanks and gratitude to a range of organizations and individuals, without whom this year's conference would not take place. This conference would have not materialized without the efforts of the contributing **authors for sharing the fruit of their research and the reviewers for scrutinizing**, despite their busy schedules. We also thank **our members and colleagues who accepted the duty to participate in the Scientific Committee** and for their valuable help in the screening, selecting, and recommending best contributions.

All submitted conference papers are peer-reviewed by three authorized referees.

All presentations made during the congress were published on the social media accounts of the CEO Congress. It can also be downloaded from the links below.

Here is the link for the recording of the first day (Access code: \$6XL1\$!U):

https://duan.zoom.us/rec/share/mQxuO_ksTrl9tGPup_8zME5P4SBXVbx7dXISngQtM9GWBfQ2SngClOmLWDh0rxs.FJ8-AHsEm77sZ84W

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(İletişim, Ekonomi, Organizasyon)
Sosyal Bilimler Kongresi

24-25 Aralık 2021 tarihlerinde "**3. Uluslararası CEO İletişim, Ekonomi ve Organizasyon Sosyal Bilimler Kongresi**" Alfred Nobel University ev sahipliğinde **Ukrayna**'da Mohanlal Sukhadia University, **International Vision University**, Samarkand Branch of Tashkent University of Economics, **International Gorazde University**, Nişantaşı Üniversitesi, **Cyprus West University**, University of Prizren, **NCM Yayıncılık** ve Insec iş birliği ile gerçekleştirilmiştir.

Kongremizde *Afganistan, Arjantin, Arnavutluk, Avustralya, Azerbaycan, Bulgaristan, Endonezya, Fas, Filipinler, Gürcistan, Hindistan, İtalya, Japonya, Kuzey Kıbrıs Türk Cumhuriyeti, Kırgızistan, Kolombiya, Kosova, Makedonya, Nijerya, Özbekistan, Pakistan, Polonya, Sırbistan, Şili, Türkiye, Romanya, Sri Lanka, Tunus, Birleşik Krallık, Yeni Zelanda, Vietnam, Zambiya* gibi **32 ülkeden** ve **114 kurum/üniversiteden 164 akademisyen** tarafından hazırlanan **112 bildiri** sunulmuştur.

Kongremize 137 bildiri özeti gönderilmiş, editör ve hakem süreçlerinden sonra bunlardan 114 tanesi sözlü sunuma kabul edilmiş, ancak **16 oturumda 112 bildirinin sunumu** gerçekleştirilmiştir. Sunulan bildirilerin tam metinleri, **978-605-73822-0-7** ISBN'li bu tam metin e-kitapta tam metin bildiri olarak yayımlanmaktadır. Tüm sorularınız için ceocongress.info@gmail.com adresine e_mail gönderilebilir.

Kongrede sunulan 112 bildirinin 76'sı yurt dışındandır. Yayımlanan özet **bildirilerin % 68'i Türkiye dışındandır. Tam metin kitabında yayınlanan tam metin bildirilerin ise %62'si Türkiye dışındandır. Önceki Uluslararası CEO Kongre'lerde olduğu gibi 3. Uluslararası CEO Kongre'de de hem bildiri özet kitabında hem de bildiri tam metin kitabında yabancı oranı %50'den fazladır.**

Onaylı, sunumu yapılmış ve yayınlanan **112 bildiriden altısına en iyi bildiri ödülü duyurulmuştur.**

Kongre esnasında gerçekleşen tüm sunumlar kongrenin sosyal medya hesaplarında yayımlanmıştır. Tekrar yararlanmak istendiği durumlarda CEO Congress sosyal medya hesaplarından izlenebilir. Bununla birlikte aşağıdaki linklerden indirilmesi de mümkündür.

Gönderilen tüm konferans bildirileri, kör hakemli gözden geçirilmektedir.

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Kongrenin bilim insanlarına, kamu ve özel sektör ile STK'ların yönetiminin etkinliğine katkı bulunmasını temenni eder, bildirileriyle katkıda bulunan akademisyenler ile düzenleme kurulu, danışma kurulu, bilim ve hakem kurulundaki meslektaşlarımıza ziyadesiyle teşekkür ederiz.

A Special Thanks To...

Below is a list of individuals who have supported **CEO Congress 2021 Ukraine** by donating some of their time. It is these people who make our work possible and have been a great help. We would like to say a special THANK YOU for all those listed below.

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Comparison of Data Mining Methods: Interest Rate Estimation Application

PhD(c). Enes KOÇOĞLU

Türkiye Emlak Katılım Bankası A.Ş
enes-kocoglu@hotmail.com
Orcid: 0000-0002-7137-5323

Prof.Dr. Filiz ERSÖZ

Karabuk University
fersoz@karabuk.edu.tr
Orcid: 0000-0002-4964-8487

ABSTRACT

Today, most of the countries deal with the management of basic economic problems such as inflation, interest, exchange rate and unemployment rate. The main cause of economic problems in developing countries is due to insufficient capital. Country managers make financial decisions, such as the interest rate, which allows foreign capital to come to the country. This study was conducted to compare three machine learning methods that can be used to develop an estimation method based on quantitative data that banks may need in order to determine the correct price while pricing their loans to their customers. In the research, the variables affecting the interest rate were determined by decision tree analysis; The most important variable affecting the interest rate in an increase or decrease direction has been the inflation rate. The second important variable affecting the interest rate is the unemployment rate.

Keywords: Banking, Interest rate, Data Mining, Machine Learning, SVM, Random Forest, Decision Tree.

INTRODUCTION

It is thought that the birth of banking started with the giving of the gold entrusted to the clergy by the clergy to the people in need. The fact that the clergy demanded a certain amount of money while lending to the temples to generate income led to the rise of interest. Although banking activities have diversified in the changing and developing world economy, the main purpose of banks has not changed.

The main purpose of banking; to transfer funds from those who have surplus funds to those who need funds, in return for a certain interest income. The inconsistency between the promised repayment term and the promised repayment term when collecting funds, increases the importance of predicting how the interest rate will change in the future in the market. For example, since it collects deposits with a maturity of 1 month and extends the loan with a maturity of 24 months, the bank has to estimate the interest rate risk with a maturity of 23 months.

The interest rate decisions taken are directly related to the activities of the banks operating in the country. A bank should be able to predict interest rate changes that may occur within a certain period of time while giving loans or collecting deposits, so that it can make accurate pricing. While qualitative approaches were applied in decision-making processes until the 1950s, today's developing data mining methods can learn from past data and make predictions for the future.

The development of technology has increased the speed of formation and dissemination of data. Rapidly spreading data creates ever-growing data clouds like snowballs. Retrospective analysis of data with traditional statistical methods is insufficient in increasing data sizes. Today, the complexity of the problems has accelerated the development of methods that learn from data and can make possible predictions for the future according to what is learned. These methods are called data mining methods.

Data mining methods have been used for academic studies in many different fields such as finance, banking, health, textile, and production, and it has been seen to be successful. Developing technology has increased the number of data as well as the possibility of data not showing normal distribution. Traditional statistical methods are insufficient today because the data do not show normal distribution and the difficulty of analysis arises from the increase in the amount of data (Asareh & Ghaeli, 2019; Bayram & Dündar, 2021; Çavuşoğlu & Kaçar, 2019; Diaz et al., 2016; Enke & Thawornwong, 2005; F. Ersöz, 2019b, 2019a; T. Ersöz et al., 2018, 2016; Koçoğlu & Ersöz, 2021; Simsek et al., 2020; Ünver et al., 2018).

Data mining is the process of discovering patterns involving methods at the intersection of machine learning, statistics, and can meaningfully extract valuable information from big data sets. Machine learning, financial data analysis is used in many financial institutes for accurate analysis of consumer data. For example; predict defaults, fast and save time, make credit decisions, categorize customers directly (Damrongsakmethee & Neagoe, 2017).

It has been seen in the literature that studies on interest rate estimation are carried out with econometric methods and studies with data mining methods are insufficient. The excess of data in the banking sector creates an opportunity for the development of data mining methods.

This study was conducted to compare three machine learning methods that can be used to develop an estimation method based on quantitative data that banks may need in order to determine the correct price while pricing their loans to their customers. The compared methods were chosen from among the methods that are seen to be used most in the literature. As a result of the literature review, it has been seen that Random Forest, Decision Tree and SVM algorithms from machine learning algorithms are frequently used in solving estimation problems. The aim is to determine the algorithm that can be preferred for decision makers when

needed. The importance of this is to increase the ability of decision makers to make appropriate choices among many existing algorithms.

1. LITERATURE

According to the summary of the literature review presented in Table 2, the most commonly used variables among the variables affecting the interest rate were USD Selling Price, Inflation Rate, CPI, Stocks, Industrial Production Index, Gold Selling Price, Government Domestic Debt Securities, and others, in the order of importance. In this study, the variables of "M" (Central Bank Gold Reserve) and "C" (Government Domestic Debt Securities) were included, considering that they could affect interest rates based on expert opinions in addition to the literature review.

Table 1. Variables Used in the Study

CODE	VARIABLES
A	Loan Interest Rate
C	Government Domestic Debt Securities
D	Foreign Debt Principal and Interest
E	Total Credit Volume
G	USD Selling Price
L	Euro Selling Price
M	Central Bank Gold Reserve
N	Central Bank Gross Currency Reserve
Y	Industrial Production Index
Z	Employment Rate (%)
X	Unemployment Rate (%)
W	Inflation Rate (%)
P	Consumer price index (%)
B2	Stock Index (BIST100)
XAU	Gold Selling Price

Summary of the literature review regarding variables is presented in Table 2. In the study model, which was established with a total of 14 independent variables and one dependent variable, the variables were created by making use of the variables found in the literature.

Table 2. Literature Summary on Economic Indicators

Author	Variables Used in the Research													
	A	C	D	E	G	M	N	Y	Z	X	W	P	B2	XAU
(Telçeken & Değirmen, 2019)	x										x	x		
(Aksu & Emsen, 2019)	x				x						x	x		
(Yenice & Yenisu, 2019)	x				x						x			
(Yelghi et al., 2021)	x				x						x			
(Thakur et al., 2016)	x				x							x		
(Gupta & Kotzé, 2015)	x				x							x		

(Tursoy, 2019)	x					x
(Assefa et al., 2017)	x					x
(Kim & Shi, 2018)	x	x			x	
(Apergis et al., 2019)	x					x
(Stolyarov & Tesar, 2019)	x	x		x	x	x
(Diaz et al., 2016)	x		x	x	x	x
(Oh & Han, 2000)	x		x	x		x

When the literature was examined, it was seen that there were two studies using the variables in the research. In this study, the variables of central bank gold reserve and government domestic debt securities were included.

2. METHODOLOGY

In this study, monthly data of the variables, which were thought to affect the interest rates in Turkey between the dates of 2014 - 2021, were used for analysis. The data of the study consisted of the open-source data published on tcmb.gov.tr and investing.com websites. The data set used in the study was selected based on the literature and expert opinion, as presented in Table 1.

As a result of the literature review, it has been seen that Random Forest, Decision Tree and Support Vector Machines (SVM) algorithms from machine learning algorithms are frequently used in solving estimation problems. For this reason, three algorithms, which are frequently used in this study, were compared on the same data set. The aim is to determine the algorithm that can be preferred for decision makers when needed. The importance of this is to increase the ability of decision makers to make appropriate choices among many existing algorithms.

The compared methods were chosen from among the methods that are seen to be used most in the literature. As a result of the literature review, it has been seen that Random Forest, Decision Tree and SVM algorithms from machine learning algorithms are frequently used in solving estimation problems (Harimoorthy & Thangavelu, 2021; Pranckevičius & Marcinkevičius, 2017; Shaikhina et al., 2019). The aim is to determine the algorithm that can be preferred for decision makers when needed. The importance of this is to increase the ability of decision makers to make appropriate choices among many existing algorithms.

Accuracy rate, precision, sensitivity, measurements were used for comparing the prediction performances of the algorithms used in the study. The precision value shows how many of the predicted values in the test set are actually correct. It is defined as the prediction accuracy rate divided by the total accuracy rate. The sensitivity value defines how many of the predictions that should be predicted positively are predicted positively. Accuracy rate is calculated by dividing the correct predictions by the total number of predictions. This is the most important factor in comparing methods.

3. Comparison of Algorithms

According to the analysis performed on the monthly data, all algorithms used were found to have a high rate of success in terms of classification accuracy, as presented in Table 3. When the algorithms were ranked from high to low according to the Accuracy rate, the sequence of the classification algorithms was Decision Tree, Random Forest, SVM.

Table 3. Comparison

Method	Class	Precision	Sensitivity	Accuracy Statistics
Decision Tree	Low Interest	1.000	1.000	0.988
	Normal Interest	1.000	1.000	
	High Interest	0.970	1.000	
	Very High Interest	1.000	0.970	
Random Forest	Low Interest	1.000	0.833	0.976
	Normal Interest	0.923	1.000	
	High Interest	1.000	0.970	
	Very High Interest	0.970	1.000	
SVM	Low Interest	1.000	1.000	0.882
	Normal Interest	1.000	0.667	
	High Interest	0.750	1.000	
	Very High Interest	1.000	0.857	

Comparing the “Precision values” presented in Table 3, the precision values in low, normal and high interest environments are ranked from highest to lowest from Decision Tree, Random Forest, SVM algorithms, respectively. This determination shows that the accuracy rate and the precision value are parallel.

When they were ranked from high to low in terms of sensitivity values, the sequence was the Decision Tree, Random Forest, SVM algorithms. The higher value of the Decision Tree algorithm compared to other algorithms according to sensitivity is significant in terms of risky decisions. Sensitivity is an important parameter as the loan interest decision directly affects the profitability of a bank.

4. CONCLUSION

This study was conducted to compare three machine learning methods that can be used to develop an estimation method based on quantitative data that banks may need in order to determine the correct price while pricing their loans to their customers. The compared methods were chosen from among the methods that are seen to be used most in the literature. As a result of the literature review, it has been seen that Random Forest, Decision Tree and SVM algorithms from machine learning algorithms are frequently used in solving estimation problems. The aim is to determine the algorithm that can be preferred for decision makers when needed. The importance of this is to increase the ability of decision makers to make appropriate choices among many existing algorithms.

According to the results of the decision tree analysis; The most important variable was the inflation rate. The second important variable was the unemployment rate. In the decision tree, which is classified according to the inflation rate, when inflation rises above 19%, the interest rate becomes 60% very high and 40% high. In the decision tree classified according to the inflation rate, in cases where inflation is higher than 19%, the interest rate is 60% very high and 40% high. Analysis results show that; The main problem of the economy is either a very high

or very low interest rate environment. While investments decrease in a very high interest environment, investments decrease due to high exchange rates in a very low interest environment. These two important situations are the risk environments that banks should be able to anticipate. For this reason, the success of Decision Tree algorithms is considered as an important result in this study.

The results of the analysis, it was determined that the three algorithms compared had a high success rate in terms of accuracy. Algorithms are ranked according to their accuracy as Decision Tree, Random Forest, SVM from high to low. When the precision and precision values of the three algorithms are compared, the results seem to be in line with the accuracy rate. This shows that decision makers can consider the accuracy rate as the only factor.

In this study, the success of machine learning methods in financial data analysis has been demonstrated. In addition to the comparison of machine learning methods, the underlying economic problem of the study is the determination of the variables that affect the interest rate. The most important variable affecting the interest rate from the results of the study is the inflation rate, and the second is the unemployment rate. Today, most of the countries are trying to make decisions within the paradox of interest rate and inflation rate. This result, which was revealed in this study as a very important information for the economic strategies of the countries, should be investigated with other studies.

REFERENCES

- Aksu, H., & Emsen, Ö. S. (2019). Enflasyon, Faiz ve Döviz Kuru İlişkileri: Türkiye için ARDL Analizleri ile Asimetrik Eş - Bütünleşme Araştırması. *İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Dergisi*, 33(1), 69–90.
- Apergis, N., Cooray, A., Khraief, N., & Apergis, I. (2019). Do Gold Prices Respond to Real Interest Rates? Evidence From the Bayesian Markov Switching VECM Model. *Journal of International Financial Markets, Institutions and Money*, 60, 134–148.
- Asareh, B., & Ghaeli, M. R. (2019). Valuation and Assessment of Customers in Banking Industry Using Data Mining Techniques. *International Journal of Data and Network Science*, 3(2), 93–102.
- Assefa, T. A., Esqueda, O. A., & Varella, A. (2017). Stock Returns and Interest Rates Around the World: A Panel Data Approach. *Journal of Economics and Business*, 89, 20–35.
- Bayram, S. S., & Dündar, S. (2021). Türkiye’de Banka Şubesi Lokasyonunun Veri Madenciliği ile Analizi. *Journal of International Banking Economy and Management Studies*, 4(1), 34–52.
- Çavuşoğlu, Ü., & Kaçar, S. (2019). Anormal Trafik Tespiti için Veri Madenciliği Algoritmalarının Performans Analizi. *Academic Platform Journal of Engineering and Science*, 7(2), 205–216.
- Damrongsakmethee, T., & Neagoe, V. (2017). Data Mining and Machine Learning for Financial Analysis. *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*, 10(39).
- Diaz, D., Theodoulidis, B., & Dupouy, C. (2016). Modelling and Forecasting Interest Rates During Stages of the Economic Cycle : A Knowledge-Discovery Approach. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 44, 245–264.
- Enke, D., & Thawornwong, S. (2005). The Use of Data Mining and Neural Networks for Forecasting Stock Market Returns. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 29(4), 927–940.
- Ersöz, F. (2019a). Data Mining and Text Mining with Big Data: Review of Differences. *International Journal of Recent Advances in Multidisciplinary Research*, 06(01), 4391–4395.
- Ersöz, F. (2019b). Dijitalleşme Çağında Büyük Veri ve Analitiği: Sektörel Uygulamalar. In *4 th International Congress on 3D Printing (Additive Manufacturing) Technologies and Digital Industry* (pp. 712–720).
- Ersöz, T., Ersöz, F., & Merdin, D. (2018). Performance Measurement in Business. *Baltic Journal of Real Estate Economics and Construction Management*, 9671, 272–284.
- Ersöz, T., Ersöz, F., & Özbilge, S. (2016). Determination of the Bank’s Customer Risk Profile : Data Mining Applications. *World Academy of Science, Engineering and Technology International Journal of Economics and Management Engineering*, 10(6), 2199–2203.

- Gupta, R., & Kotzé, K. (2015). The Role of Oil Prices in the Forecasts of South African Interest Rates : A Bayesian Approach. *University of Pretoria Department of Economics Working Paper Series*, 31, 1–16.
- Harimoorthy, K., & Thangavelu, M. (2021). Multi-Disease Prediction Model Using Improved SVM-Radial Bias Technique in Healthcare Monitoring System. *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing*, 3715–3723.
- Kim, H., & Shi, W. (2018). The Determinants of the Benchmark Interest Rates in China. *Journal of Policy Modeling*, 40(2), 395–417.
- Koçoğlu, E., & Ersöz, F. (2021). Data Mining Application For Decision Optimization at Risk. *International Journal Of 3D Printing Technologies and Digital Industry*, 5(2), 195–209.
- Oh, K. J., & Han, I. (2000). Using Change-Point Detection to Support Artificial Neural Networks for Interest Rates Forecasting. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 19(2), 105–115.
- Pranckevičius, T., & Marcinkevičius, V. (2017). Comparison of Naïve Bayes, Random Forest, Decision Tree, Support Vector Machines and Logistic Regression Classifiers for Text Reviews Classification. *Baltic J. Modern Computing*, 5(2), 221–232.
- Shaikhina, T., Lowe, D., Daga, S., Briggs, D., Higgins, R., & Khovanova, N. (2019). Biomedical Signal Processing and Control Decision Tree and Random Forest Models for Outcome Prediction in Antibody Incompatible Kidney Transplantation. *Biomedical Signal Processing and Control*, 52, 456–462.
- Simsek, S., Kursuncu, U., Kibis, E., Anisabdellatif, M., & Dag, A. (2020). A Hybrid Data Mining Approach for Identifying the Temporal Effects of Variables Associated with Breast Cancer Survival. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 139, 1–13.
- Stolyarov, D., & Tesar, L. L. (2019). Interest Rate Trends in a Global Context. *Michigan Retirement Research Center Research Paper*, 402, 1–60.
- Telçeken, H., & Değirmen, S. (2019). Enflasyon ve Kredi Faizleri Arasındaki Uzun Dönemli İlişkinin Fisher Hipotezi Çerçevesinde Değerlendirilmesi: Türkiye Uygulaması. *Istanbul Business Research*, 47(2), 154–182.
- Thakur, G. S. M., Bhattacharya, R., & Mondal, S. S. (2016). Artificial Neural Network Based Model for Forecasting of Inflation in India. *Fuzzy Information and Engineering*, 8(1), 87–100.
- Tursoy, T. (2019). The Interaction Between Stock Prices and Interest Rates in Turkey: Empirical Evidence from ARDL Bounds Test Cointegration. *Financial Innovation*, 5(7).
- Ünver, M., Sahin, B., & Ersöz, F. (2018). An Application of Logistics Regression Model to Determining the Credit Suitability and Impacting Factors in a Special Bank Branch. *Communication in Mathematical Modelling and Applications*, 3(1), 1–12.
- Yelghi, A., Gürsoy, M., & Yelghi, A. (2021). Bankacılık Piyasasında Kredi Türüme Göre Belirlenen Faiz Oranlarının Enflasyon Ve Döviz Kuru İlişkisi. *Journal of Empirical Economics and Social Sciences*, 3(1), 21–42.
- Yenice, S., & Yenisu, E. (2019). Türkiye’de Döviz Kuru, Enflasyon ve Faiz Oranlarının Etkileşimi. *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*, 22(4), 1521–1546.